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**LEGITIMIZING IDENTITIES THROUGH VULGARITY: THE STUDY OF EPISODE
FIVE IN *SELINA TESTED* SERIES**

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Abstract

This paper explores how the movie series ‘Selina Tested’ employs vulgarity as a narrative device to construct a unique social group identity. Halliday’s (1967) anti-language, a linguistic identity based on social group, is adopted for the study. The study adopts a qualitative research approach where episode five (5) of the movie (Fracas) provides sufficient data for analysis. Using the thematic analysis approach, the study examines how vulgarity, viewed here as anti-language, is used to subvert conventional means and standard forms of communication. The findings reveal that the dominant use of vulgarity or anti-language elements by the young characters in ‘Selina Tested’ sets them (the young characters) apart from the normal society as a distinct social group. The most prominent anti-language elements found in ‘Selina Tested’ include the wholesale use of a distinct vocabulary popular among the youth on ‘Holy Ground’ (the major setting in the movie), distorted word order, relexification and the use of unconventional codes. With these findings, the research makes a significant to the ongoing discussion on the role of media in shaping identity and culture, highlighting the potential of anti-languages as instruments of empowerment. The study recommends ‘Selina Tested’ to functional linguists and scholars with interests in language and identity constructions as a good source of data.

Keywords: Anti-language, codes, language and identity, movie, social identity

Introduction

One of the most important properties of man and his society is language. Language is the means through which people express and transmit their culture across generations. There are many definitions of language that represent various linguistic movements. Rekpa (2020) identifies two approaches to the definition of language; the syntactocentric and the communicative perspectives. Led by Noam Chomsky, the syntactocentric approach sees language more from the position of form than of function. According to Chomsky (1957:13), language is ‘a set of sentences, each finite in length and constructed of a finite set of elements.’ Chomsky claims that language is not properly regarded as a system of communication. It is a system for expressing thought, something quite different. It can of course be used for communication, as anything people do – manner of walking or style of clothes or hair for example. But in any useful sense of the term, communication is not the function of language, and may even be of no unique significance for understanding the functions and nature of language’ (Chomsky (2000:75).

The communicative perspective on the other hand, views language from a functional point of view. One of the prominent linguists who holds this view is MAK Halliday. According to Halliday (1979), language is a means of expressing what the human organism can do, in interaction with other human organisms. Halliday opines that people use language to interact with one another, to construct and maintain their interpersonal relationships and social order that lies behind them, and in doing so they interpret and represent the world for one another and for themselves. In a similar view, Yule, G. (2010) posits that a language is a set of resources that are available to language users for the symbolization of thought, and for the communication of these symbolizations. Yule further argues that language is shaped and constrained by the functions it serves. Yule is corroborated by Aza, (2018) who states that language is a system of conventional spoken or written symbols by means of which human beings, as members of a social group and participants in its

culture, express themselves. According to Honorary, the functions of language include communication, the expression of identity, play, imaginative expression, and emotional release.

It is obvious from the above definitions that Halliday, (1967), Taylor, (2002) and Honorary, (2021) view language as a system of function. They view language from the perspective of what people do with language, rather than what language is. This view of language is essentially quite popular in linguistics as more people consider language as a system of functions than those who do not (Aza, 2018). This study takes a bearing from this definition to explore how vulgarity is used as a tool to construct identity.

Literature Review

When people speak, they construct unique identities depending on the context and their specific circumstances. According to Djité (2006), identity is the everyday word for people's sense of who they are. Sarah (2018) simply believes that the term identity literally refers to sameness. Additionally, identity can refer to an individual's own subjective sense of self, to personal classification markers that appear as important, both to oneself and to others, and also to those markers that delineate group membership(s) (Edwards, 2009). As Norton (2013) cogently noted, identity is the way a person understands his or her relationship to the world, how that relation is constructed across time and space and how the person understands possibilities for the future. Effectively, the relationship between language and identity does not only describe kinds of speech, but the kinds of speakers who produce or construct certain kinds of identity through their use of language. Elements that determine identity are those related to age, gender, occupation, class, region, ethnicity and social group. Halliday (2009) confirms this by stating that language can both give someone identity and allows them to share the aspects of it, such as their age, gender or where they live.

There are many sociolinguistics theories that look at the relationship between language and identity. These include accommodation theory, social identity theory, critical language and identity theory and intersectionality theory (Hall, 2003). But those that examine specific elements of identity include Carmen Llasman's (2000) regional identity, John Shuttleworth's (1999) gender identity, Gary Ives's (2001) age identity, Michael Nelson's (2000) occupation identity and MAK Halliday's (1976) anti-language identity, which is based on social group. The focus of this paper is to examine the use of Halliday's anti-language as a means of social group identity in the popular YouTube movie titled 'Selina Tested'.

Language and identity research have attracted a lot of interests in the field of social sciences and linguistics over the past decades (Djité, 2006; Edwards, 2009; Nordquist, 2024). According to Hall, (2003), until recently, the concept of identity has taken a central position in linguistic anthropology, serving less as the background for other kinds of investigation and more as a topic meriting study in its own right. Identity work frequently involves obscuring differences among those with a common identity; it may also serve to manufacture or underscore differences between in-group members and those outside the group. The perception of shared identity often requires as its foil a sense of alterity, of others who can be positioned against those socially constituted as the same (Barth 1986).

Shahrebabaki (2018) explains that sometimes, individual speakers maintain dual identities by the use of two linguistic varieties to communicate in double speech communities. Shahrebabaki suggests that identity may change in different ways through time. Within a speech community, speakers continuously adjust their identities and contribute to the group's whole identity. Nordquist, (2018) states that research interests in the relationship between identity and language underwent a shift in the epistemological paradigms utilised by many second language acquisition scholars and linguistic anthropologists. Questions on identity and language learning have taken up

new research trajectories theoretically and empirically, and she claims that language forms a central role in defining social and political organisations, which is essential to the way in which post-structuralism depicts individual diversity (Alshehri, 2023).

‘Selina Tested’ is a popular movie series on YouTube in Nigeria, which has received limited scholarly attention (Nwakeochina & Etifit, 2021). Two reasons could account for this; in addition to being a relatively new series produced only in 2021, it portrays street life which some scholars may find unserious and abhorring. Nwakeochina and Etifit (2021) describe ‘Selina Tested’ as a movie characterised by vulgarism and streetism.

One prominent work on ‘Selina Tested’ is a research by Nwakeocha and Etifit, (2021) who examine language vulgarism and streetism in ‘Selina Tested’. The research attempts to explore how the use of vulgar language and violent behaviour in home videos in Nigeria influence the audience of these home videos. The research concludes that the ‘Selina Tested’ has a huge influence on the audience exposed to the heavy violent scenes, language vulgarity and streetism. The study also suggests that vulgar language and violent behaviour in home movies has negatively influence the audience, especially the youth. It recommends caution on the side of movie producers in managing vulgar language and violent behaviour in home movies.

This study, however, departs from Nwakeocha and Etifit’s focus. It examines vulgarity with the aim of discovering how it can be used as a tool for creating unique identities rather than on how it influences social behaviour. The current research therefore makes a novel contribution towards recent discussions on and around language and identity.

Research Methodology

Based on the source of data and type of analysis, this study lends itself to the paradigm of qualitative research. Data for this study consists of the narrative elements in episode five (5) of ‘Selina Tested’ (retrieved from YouTube). These elements include dialogue, character development and plot. Episode five was selected for the significant availability of anti-language elements in the episode. Twenty anti-language elements were identified and analysed qualitatively. The analysis was done using a thematic analysis approach which involves identification and coding of patterns in a narrative. The analysis focused on vulgar language and how it is used in the movie to construct identity.

Theoretical framework

This paper examines vulgarity in ‘Selina Tested’ through the lens of MAK Halliday’s (1967) anti-language, also known as social group identity theory. Halliday defines anti-language as the language of an anti-society that exists as an alternative to ‘normal’ society. It is linked to identity because it is used when a group of people seek to establish a covert identity. The major findings of Halliday are that anti-languages are generally shown through a specific lexicon; they share the same grammar as the main language but have a different vocabulary; users of anti-languages can communicate meaning to each other that is inaccessible to a non-user; groups who use anti-language view it as fundamental to their identity. It can be used by those inside a group who share ideas and attitudes as a way of distinguishing themselves from others (Yule, 2010). The need to create social boundaries and exclude non-members of a particular group can lead to the emergence of an anti-language variety.

In a similar submission, Montgomery (1986) states that anti-languages are basically created by a process of relexicalisation which is the substitution of new words for old. Montgomery further states that in the case of anti-language, the grammar of the parent language may be preserved, but

a distinctive vocabulary develops especially in activities and areas that set it off from the established society. In agreement with Halliday and Montgomery, Nordquist (2018) states that anti-language is a minority dialect or method of communicating within a minority speech community that excludes members of the main speech community. It serves to create and maintain social structures through conversation, just as an everyday language does; but the social structure is of a particular kind, in which certain elements are strongly foregrounded. This gives anti-language a special character in which metaphorical modes of expression are the norms. Nordquist explains anti-language even deeper by stating that patterns of this kind appear at all levels: phonological, lexico-grammatical and semantic. It can be seen from Nordquist's explanation that anti-language codes can arise from phonemes, word choices or alternative meaning of existing words.

Nordquist, (2018) provides examples of anti-language varieties around the world to include, Nadsat, Polari, Backslang and Grypsera. Nadsat is derived from Russian, British, and Cockney rhyming slang. Elements of the language were inspired by the Edwardian stutters and British teenagers in the late 1950s who carried out violent attacks on innocent people. Rhyming slang is characteristic of London's East End, where speakers substitute random rhyming words for others: for example, 'nasty' (cornish pasty); 'key' (Bruce Lee); and so on. Polari is an example of an anti-language that was used in the UK by gay men but has now been out of use. The lexicon was derived from a variety of sources including Cockney rhyming slang, backslang, Italian and drug-users slang. Backslang is a form of anti-language where words are said as if they are spelt backwards. For example, 'erif (fire), 'doog eno' (good one), 'delo', (old). It enabled gay men speak without being understood. **Grypsera** is originally a polish dialect. Grypsera borrows from Yiddish, Ukrainia, Russian and German and is used as a criminal code by inmates of the Polish prison system. Over time Grypsera moved away from Polish language and started using vowel sounds

not used in the Polish language, making it quite a unique language in its own right (Nordquist, 2018:7).

Selina Tested: A background

‘Selina Tested’ is a popular action movie series on YouTube that has caught the interest of many Nigerians especially the youth. It is produced by Munachim Praize, also known as Odogwu, a young man who grew up in Port Harcourt, Rivers State of Nigeria, where he had developed his interest in acting and audio productions. It is acted in pidgin, dominated by youth characters and represents a group identity. ‘Selina Tested’ was shot in Obi Akpor Local Government Area, Rivers State of Nigeria (Nwakeocha and Etifit 2021). Nwakeocha and Itifit describe ‘Selina Tested’ as an action movie that depicts violence, power/authority/dominance, comedy, revenge drama, betrayal, survival, love and romance.

Set on a small location called ‘Holy Ground’, the movie mostly revolves around two major characters, Aboy and Chiboy who have conquered and now rule Holy Ground. They grew up to face a life of struggle and survival, hence they must be ‘selina tested’ (i.e., fortified) in order to survive the challenges that confront them on a daily basis. The protagonist, Aboy himself grew up without his parents who had been murdered by his uncle over land disputes. As an action movie, ‘Selina Tested’ portrays a lot of crime and violent scenes, unfolding in short episodes of between 25-35 minutes.

A summary of episode 5

Episode 5 is titled ‘Fracas’, which itself is an anti-language term meaning misunderstanding. It opens with Odogwu sending his niece Bellema, with drugs (i.e., sandas) to deliver to a customer. Shortly after Bellema leaves, Aboy steps in and requests some money from Odogwu to help him’

‘do one waka’ (travel). Odogwu refuses to lend Aboy ‘robbers’ (money) because according to him, Aboy has betrayed ‘brotherhood’ by refusing to execute Tallest, a sworn enemy of their group comprising Odogwu, Aboy and Chiboy when he had the opportunity. Aboy’s decision to ‘freestyle’ (pardon) Tallest sparked off a faceoff (fracas) between two best friends (suicides), Aboy and Chiboy. Meanwhile as the misunderstanding between Aboy and Chiboy lingers, their fierce rival, Sibi, plans to take advantage of the situation and widen the crack in their camp. Sibi ‘put the hit’ (murders Chiboy’s mother) that would become the catalyst for unending conflicts in the rest of the movie. Most of the actions leading to the subsequent episodes have been catalysed by this audacious act, the murder of Chiboy’s mother.

Data Analysis

Anti-language elements in Selina Tested

Selina Tested provides a clear example of what Halliday (1967) sees as a social group with a unique identity that sets them apart from a ‘normal’ society. Both the action and the language of the movie portray the major setting of the movie, Holly Ground as a place for social group activities. Twenty anti-language terms were identified in episode 5 and were analysed. In the analysis, each identified anti-language term is provided with the Standard English equivalent suggested beside it. The context from which it was extracted is provided, and then the analysis follows.

Anti-language elements used in the dialogue between Aboy and Odogwu

Robbers- money

Play tape- inform

Suicide- friend

Dialogue/analysis

Aboy: Odogwu, e get one or two waka wey I wan do. You fit tender me **robbers** make I dey push?

I beg.

Odogwu: Mek I tender you robbers? How? You think say I never hear your hans? Dem don **play** me de **tape** as how you dey go jump jump dey betray betray your **suicides** dem.

The dialogue between Aboy and Odogwu above is so closely coded that the audience has to share the knowledge of the codes before they can understand the conversation. Aboy approaches Odogwu to ‘tender him robbers’ (give him money) to help him ‘waka’ (travel). Odogwu declines. ‘Make I tender you robbers?’ How?’ Odogwu asks why he should lend him money when he is angry with him for betraying him and his friends. ‘You think say I no hear your hans?’ dem don play me de tape as you go dey jump jump dey betray betray your suicides dem’. Odogwu reveals to Aboy that he is aware that he (Aboy) is a betrayer who betrays his friends (suicides dem) because he had been informed (dem don play me the tape).

Anti-language elements in the dialogue between Tallest and Sibi

Echo- shout

Die it- stop

Wida- stop (can also mean ‘what?’)

Lai mohammed- lie

Cap-tell

Legit- truth

Tuama- run

Ododo- power/audacity

Manchi- man

Whine- deceive

Nono- marijuana (also means to smoke)

Dialogue/analysis

Tallest: ... as I **echo**, I jas up, I ras everbody come dey say **die it!** Aboy, Chiboy, Odogwu, Amourer, dem **tuama** for the ama. Dem confirm de **ododo**. Dem come dey fear say which **manchi** me I be.

Sibi: Tallest, Tallest, why you dey **whine** me nah? I be like I be chais man for your eyes? **Wida** your **lie mohammed** nah Tallest. Tallest **cap** me the **legit**.

Tallest: I beg gimme nono mek I nono.

Tallest, assumed to have been murdered by Aboy and his friends, suddenly reappears at his friend, Sibi's house. In surprise Sibi asks how he escaped from the rival group and he lies: '...as I echo, I jas up! I ras everybody come dey say die it'. He claims he overpowered his enemies when he roared (echo). According to tallest, Aboy, Chiboy and Amoura all ran away in fear (tuama). Sibi does not believe Tallest, thus the question, 'Tallest, why you dey whine me nah?' Meaning why

are you lying to me? ‘Wida your lai mohammed nah’, meaning stop lying! ‘Cap me de legit’ (tell me the truth). In ‘dem confirm de ododo’ Tallest means Aboy and his friends confirmed that he is more powerful than them, and that is why they ran away (tuama). Before Tallest leaves Sibi’s house, he asks for marijuana (nono) to smoke (make I nono). ‘Nono’ here is both a noun and verb- marijuana (noun), smoke (verb). The language use above is almost entirely strange to whoever does not share the knowledge of these codes. Such kinds of scenarios abound in the ‘Selina Tested’.

Anti-language elements in the confrontation between Chiboy and Trigger

Lap- come

Mount excess- monitor

Wida- what

Dialogue/analysis

Chiboy: Hex! What’s up? Shebi you and that **manchi** follow de other day dey spoil spoil my cloth with matchete abi?

Trigger: Ehn, **wida!**

Chiboy: Wait, you dey ask me **wida...**

The encounter between Aboy and Trigger is rather a violent one. Chiboy confronts Trigger with the allegation that Trigger and another man (manchi) attacked him with a machete in his house the other day. Trigger responds in a defiant tone ‘Ehn, wida’, meaning yes, so what? ‘Wida’ does not necessarily sound rude or confrontational to a neutral audience, but Chiboy interprets it exactly for

what it is, a challenge to action. This sparks off a violent scene between Chiboy and Trigger, leading to the shedding of blood on stage.

Anti-language terms used in the encounter between Priest and Chiboy

Selina tested- fortified

Lele- problem

Chais- joke

Dialogue/Analysis

Priest: Senator Uchendu want make we lap with men wey dey **Selina tested**.

Chiboy: Priest, no **lele**. No lele. But wait, wety be de percentage?

Priest: Excess robbers... no be **chais**!

Priest comes to Chiboy to ask for men that are spiritually fortified (Selina tested) who can carry out an assignment for a politician, Senator Uchendu who wants to eliminate his political rival. Aboy responds, 'no lele', meaning there is no problem. He is ready to be part of the deal but he must know his reward; 'But wait, wety be de percentage?' Priest responds, 'Excess robbers... no be chais, meaning a lot of money (robbers). It is not a joke (no be chais).

The dialogues and analysis above show a strong determination of a group to set themselves apart from the 'normal' society through a unique language. Although the characters employ the use of a familiar language in Nigeria, Nigerian pidgin, the intentional use of numerous anti-language elements is a deliberate effort to restrict non-group members' access to the semantic properties of

the language. As Halliday suggests, an anti-language emerges when a social group desires to create a covert identity that is unique to them. The language in 'Selina Tested' reflects almost exactly this kind of scenario. While some of the words actually do exist in English but have been given coded meanings, others like 'chais', 'ododo', 'tuama', 'wida' 'lele', 'nono' 'manchi' and so on form a unique vocabulary for the language of the movie. Even within the same community, Holy Ground, only members of the in-group are able to interpret and understand the codes.

Conclusion

The relationship between language and group identities cannot be overemphasized. Linguists of the communicative background generally believe that the primary and the most important function of language is communication; other functions of language are secondary. In the course of communication however, people construct all kinds of identity like those based on gender, age, ethnicity social group and so on. This study has revealed numerous anti-language elements in 'Selina Tested'. The identified elements include relexifying, slangs and a distinctive vocabulary developed in order to set the group off from the established society. The research has also demonstrated that indeed, vulgarity can be a veritable tool for creating unique identities. 'Selina Tested' is therefore recommended to scholars whose interests are in language and identity constructions as a good source of data.

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